

THE EFFECT OF PROCESSING AND REINFORCEMENT PARAMETERS ON THE AGE-HARDENING RESPONSE OF LIQUID-PROCESSED 6061-BASED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The age hardening of 6061 based MMCs containing various types of reinforcement and produced by both rheocasting + squeeze casting, and preform infiltration has been investigated. It is shown that the ageing response of such composites is insensitive to the process route employed but dependant on the volume fraction of reinforcement. There also appears to be little effect of reinforcement size on age-hardening behaviour.

Keywords: Metal matrix composites, aluminium alloy, age-hardening

1. INTRODUCTION

A number of investigations [1,2,3] have observed that the age hardening kinetics of MMCs are more rapid than those of the unreinforced alloy and it has often been suggested that this depends on the volume fraction, size and morphology of reinforcement. Many of these effects have been attributed to an increase in dislocation density in the composite materials as a consequence of the difference in thermal expansion coefficients between the reinforcements and matrix. Other investigations [4] have suggested an effect of processing technique on ageing behaviour. For example, powder metallurgy MMCs often exhibit more rapid ageing kinetics than MMCs produced by liquid methods. However, there appear to have been very few comparative investigations where systematic observations have been made. For example, there have been few published investigations on MMCs manufactured using identical alloys and reinforcements but via different process routes.

The aim of this paper is to report results from a systematic investigation of the age hardening response of 6061-based MMCs processed by two liquid metal techniques. Rheocasting + squeeze casting, and preform infiltration have been used to produce MMCs containing various types of reinforcement ranging in size from 1 to 180 microns and ranging in volume fraction from 10 to 45%.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The MMCs employed in this work were based on a 6061 matrix. Different types of reinforcement were used including equiaxed SiC particulates (ranging from 3 to 180 microns), chopped Nicalon fibres (15 microns in diameter and 1000 microns in length) and Saffil fibres (3 microns in diameter and 150 microns in length). The volume fractions of reinforcement ranged from 10 to 45 %.

Preform Infiltration (PI) was employed for MMCs containing Saffil, Nicalon and high volume fractions of SiC particulates. Preform manufacture has been described previously [5]. The Rheocasting (R) process was employed for MMCs containing Saffil and Nicalon and for low volume fractions of SiC particulates. Details of the rheocasting process have also been described previously [1]. The main differences between the two process routes were the contact times between the reinforcement and melt (1 min for PI, 10 mins for R) and the alloy temperatures (750°C for PI, 640°C for R).

All age-hardening specimens were solution treated in air at 550°C, water quenched and aged in an oil bath at 178°C. The age-hardening response of the materials was characterised by Vickers hardness measurements (100 N load). Hardness values for the composites were an average of 10 measurements and for the preform infiltrated MMCs took into account any variation in hardness with infiltration distance [2]. Optical microscopy was carried out on selected MMC samples to examine the distribution of the reinforcements.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Composite Microstructures

Figure 1 contains micrographs of the materials used in this work. Figure 1(a) shows a typical rheocast short-fibre MMC with a random distribution of fibres. Similar microstructures were produced for the preform infiltrated short-fibre MMCs but these contained a near planar random fibre distribution. Figures 1(b),(c) and (d) show the microstructures of the SiC particulate MMCs and illustrate the effect of volume fraction and particle size on the composite microstructures.

3.2 The Effect of Processing Route

The effect of process route on age-hardening was investigated using a systematic family of short-fibre reinforced MMCs. A summary of age-hardening data for these composites is contained in Table 1. Generally there was no systematic effect of process route on the age-hardening response, with no significant differences in either the peak aged hardnesses or the kinetics of the hardening process. Table 1 also includes a comparison of unreinforced alloy data for the two process routes which shows similar results, and in addition illustrates the slightly enhanced ageing kinetics of the MMCs compared with the unreinforced alloy.

3.3 The Effect of Reinforcement Size

The effect of reinforcement size on age-hardening characteristics was investigated using two systematic SiC_p MMC families. A summary of the ageing data for these composites is contained in Table 2.

Considering first the low volume fraction SiC_p data, it is clear that in the particulate size range investigated (15-180 microns) there was no systematic effect of particle size on either the peak hardness or the ageing kinetics. This observation is confirmed by the data measured at higher volume fractions where in the particle size range 9-63 microns there was also little influence of particulate size on either the peak hardness developed or on the kinetics of the process. This suggests that for particulate sizes above 10 microns there is little influence of particle size on the age-hardening characteristics.

However, the high volume fraction data does show an effect of particle size on peak hardness below a size of 10 microns. Such an effect could result from two processes. Firstly it could arise from an enhanced hardening effect due to the fine particles themselves [6], and/or secondly due to enhanced precipitation hardening resulting from the presence of a finer scale reinforcement. The data contained in Table 2 suggests that in these composites the largest role is due to the former since the fine particulate has a very substantial effect on the solution-treated hardness (ie an enhanced hardening effect due to fine-scale reinforcement) but little systematic effect on the age-hardening increment ie $H_{PA}-H_{ST}$.

3.4 The Effect of Reinforcement Fraction

The effect of reinforcement fraction on age-hardening response was investigated using two families of composites based on short Saffil fibres and SiC particulates. A summary of this ageing data is contained in Table 3 and is plotted in Figure 2. It is clear that the behaviour of short fibre and particulate reinforced materials was similar and that as the reinforcement fraction increased both the solution-treated and peak hardnesses increased. However, Figure 2 shows that these values appear to converge at higher volume fractions which implies that the hardening potential of these composites decreases at higher volume fractions. Figure 2 also re-emphasises the effect of reinforcement size on the latent hardening potential of fine fibres or particulates since the volume fraction dependence of both H_{ST} and H_{PA} is stronger in the case of the fine 3 micron diameter Saffil fibres compared to that of the coarser SiC particulates.

The reduction in age-hardening increment ($H_{PA}-H_{ST}$) with volume fraction is clearly shown in Figure 3. However, it is interesting to note that the data lies systematically above the values calculated on the basis of a decreasing volume fraction of age-hardening matrix. This implies that the in-situ response of the composite matrix is different from that of the unreinforced alloy and is influenced by the presence of the reinforcement.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. The age-hardening response of 6061-based MMCs appears to be insensitive to the liquid process route employed.
2. The age-hardening potential of these composites is dependent on the volume fraction of reinforcement.
3. There is little effect of reinforcement size on the age-hardening characteristics of these MMCs.
4. If finer (sub 10 micron) reinforcements are employed the peak hardness developed becomes dependent on the reinforcement size (increasing with finer reinforcements).
5. The principal effect of fine-scale reinforcements appears to be due to the latent hardening potential of the reinforcement itself and not due to its influence on the age-hardening of the matrix alloy.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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6. REFERENCES

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Table 1 The Effect of Process Route on Age-Hardening

Composite	Process Route	H _{ST} [*]	H _{PA} ⁺	t _{PA} ^ϕ (mins)
10% Nicalon	R	72	135	450
9% Nicalon	PI	67	138	550
10% Saffil	R	68	134	600
8% Saffil	PI	79	145	450
Unreinforced	R	53	120	800
	PI	55	125	800

* H_{ST} - Solution-treated hardness

+ H_{PA} - Peak-aged hardness

ϕ t_{PA} - time to peak-aged hardness

Table 2 The Effect of Particle Size on Age-Hardening

Composite	Process Route	Reinforcement Size (μm)	H _{ST}	H _{PA}	t _{PA} (mins)
10% SiC _p	R	15	72	135	} ~ 500
		29	59	138	
		45	63	134	
		80	58	138	
		180	56	132	
44% SiC _p	PI	3	168	204	} ~ 300
44% SiC _p	PI	9	140	198	
48% SiC _p	PI	63	142	185	

Table 3 The Effect of Reinforcement Fraction on Age-Hardening

Reinforcement	Process Route	Volume Fraction (%)	H _{ST}	H _{PA}	t _{PA} (mins)
Saffil	PI	8	79	145	450
		17	90	155	300
		32	120	175	250
SiC _p	R	10	72	135	500
	R	20	83	147	400
	PI	48	142	185	300

Figure 1 6061-Based MMCs Reinforced with (a) 10% Chopped Nicalon (R)
 b) High Volume Fraction 63 μ m SiC_p (PI) (c) Low Volume Fraction 80 μ m SiC_p (R)
 (d) Low Volume Fraction 15 μ m SiC_p (R)

Figure 2 Effect of Volume Fraction on the Solution-treated and Peak-aged Hardness of Saffil and SiC_p Reinforced 6061

Figure 3 The Effect of Volume-Fraction on the Age-Hardening Increment, $\Delta H_v = (H_{PA} - H_{ST})$, of the Materials Contained in Table 3